

The Calculation of Sensitivity Coefficient for Depletion Equations Using Mini-Max Polynomial Approximation Method

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ABSTRACT

Depletion calculations describe the time-dependent evolution of fuel composition in reactors, which is essential for the evaluating reactor physics parameters, such as radioactivity and decay heat. As essential input parameters of depletion equations, nuclear data inherently contain a certain degree of uncertainty due to experimental measurements and evaluations. For the purpose of quantifying the propagation of nuclear data uncertainties in depletion calculations and identifying the reaction channels that have the most substantial impact on reactor performance, this paper proposes a method for calculating depletion sensitivities, named MEDM-MMPA. The method can accurately calculate the sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to nuclear data, including decay constants and microscopic cross sections. Compared with the conventional Depletion Perturbation Theory (DPT), MEDM-MMPA has a significant advantage: the sensitivity coefficients of all nuclides with respect to input parameters can be obtained by only one forward calculation, without performing separate adjoint calculations for each nuclide. The proposed method is validated by two test cases: the ^{53m}Fe decay problem and the ANL depletion benchmark, and the numerical results are presented. The results suggest that MEDM-MMPA is capable of providing the accurate solution of depletion sensitivity coefficients and offers considerable potential for sensitivity analysis in depletion calculations.

Keywords: depletion calculation, sensitivity coefficient, MEDM-MMPA

1. INTRODUCTION

Depletion calculation aims to compute the isotope composition of fuel and some other related physical parameters (decay heat, radioactivity and etc.). It is essential for reactor physics and radioactive source term analysis. However, depletion calculations are subject to a certain degree of uncertainty, which may have an impact on reactor safety. Therefore, assessing and quantifying the uncertainties in depletion calculations are conducive to improve the reliability of reactor safety analysis.

In sensitivity and uncertainty (SU) analysis, a system's uncertainty primarily arises from approximations in the computational model and inaccuracies in the input parameters. For depletion calculations, the uncertainty of computational model can be neglected due to the application of well-established matrix exponential methods in solving depletion equations. Over the past decade, the matrix exponential methods have been extensively investigated, and various approximation polynomials have been introduced to compute the matrix exponential. Representative methods include Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM)[1], Mini-Max Polynomial Approximation Method (MMPA)[2], and Laguerre Polynomials Approximation Method (LPAM)[3]. All these methods perform well in depletion calculations. Among them, CRAM is the most widely adopted in many

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depletion codes, such as ORIGEN-S[4] and NUIT[5], while MMPA is also a promising method, due to its high computational efficiency.

As previously introduced, the computational model has a negligible effect on uncertainty in depletion calculations, while the most significant source of uncertainty comes from nuclear data. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate the response of nuclide densities with respect to nuclear data through the sensitivity analysis.

The calculation of sensitivity coefficients plays an important role in sensitivity analysis. There are two commonly used approaches to determine the sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to input parameters: the Direct Differentiation Method (DDM) and the Depletion Perturbation Theory (DPT)[6]. DDM is simple to implement, but its computational cost increases with the number of input parameters. By contrast, DPT provides a significantly more efficient solution for such cases. This method has been more widely accepted for estimating the sensitivities of the depletion problems. However, in DPT, each depletion-adjoint calculation provides the sensitivity coefficient for only one nuclide with respect to nuclear data. This method becomes less computationally efficient as the number of nuclides of interest increases.

In our previous work, we proposed a novel method, named Matrix Exponential Derivative Method (MEDM)[7], for the efficient and accurate calculation of sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to nuclear data, which achieves promising results. In this paper, we applied the MMPA method within the MEDM framework and proposed the MEDM-MMPA algorithm for calculating depletion sensitivity coefficients. The theory of MEDM-MMPA will be introduced in Section 2. The numerical validation will be presented in Section 3, and the conclusion will be discussed in Section 4.

2. THEORETICAL MODELS

2.1. The Mini-Max Polynomial Approximation Method (MMPA)

The depletion equation can be written in the matrix notation as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{N}(t), \quad \mathbf{N}(0) = \mathbf{N}_0 \quad (1)$$

Where, $\mathbf{N}(t)$ is the vector of nuclide densities and \mathbf{A} is the depletion matrix which describes the transmutation relationships among all nuclides, which is composed of neutron reaction rates and decay rates.

The solution of Eq. (1) can be expressed by the form of matrix exponential

$$\mathbf{N}(t) = e^{\mathbf{A}t} \mathbf{N}(0) \quad (2)$$

Where matrix exponential $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$ is defined as the infinite Taylor series

$$e^{\mathbf{A}t} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} (\mathbf{A}t)^k \quad (3)$$

In order to solve the matrix exponential in depletion calculations, the MMPA is proposed by Yosuke Kawamoto. The objective of this method is to construct an optimal polynomial approximation $f(x)$ of the exponential function e^x around the negative real axis, in which the maximum approximation error $|f(x) - e^x|$ is minimized. And the polynomial approximation of the exponential function can be expressed by the following form

$$e^x \approx a_0 + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \left(\frac{x+c}{x-c} \right)^i \quad (4)$$

Where the range of x is $(-\infty, 0]$.

Based on the Eq. (4), the matrix exponential is represented by the mini-max polynomial approximation of the following form:

$$e^{\mathbf{A}t} \approx a_0 \mathbf{I} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \{ (\mathbf{A}t + c\mathbf{I}) (\mathbf{A}t - c\mathbf{I})^{-1} \}^i \quad (5)$$

Where a_i are real coefficients of the approximated polynomial, which can be obtained by Remez algorithm; k is the expansion order, and c is a tunable constant.

To improve the computational efficiency of MMPA, a simpler form[8] is derived based on Eq. (5). And the derivation procedure is outlined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} e^{\mathbf{A}t} &\approx a_0 \mathbf{I} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \{ (\mathbf{A}t + c\mathbf{I}) (\mathbf{A}t - c\mathbf{I})^{-1} \}^i \\ &= a_0 \mathbf{I} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \left\{ \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} + \mathbf{I} \right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \right\}^i \\ &= a_0 \mathbf{I} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \left\{ \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} + 2\mathbf{I} \right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \right\}^i \\ &= a_0 \mathbf{I} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_i \left\{ \mathbf{I} + 2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \right\}^i \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.2. Matrix Exponential Derivative Method Using MMPA

The sensitivity coefficient of the nuclide density with respect to nuclear data (decay constants, cross sections, et.al) is defined as

$$S = \frac{x}{N} \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \quad (7)$$

It can be seen that the essence of calculating the sensitivity coefficient is the evaluation of partial derivative $\partial N / \partial x$. As shown in Eq. (2), nuclide densities are obtained by the calculation of matrix exponential. Therefore, the $\partial N / \partial x$ can be calculated by computing the partial derivatives of $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$.

The key idea of the MEDM algorithm is to take the partial derivate of the matrix exponential's polynomial approximating function $f(\mathbf{A}t)$, thereby obtaining the function $f'(\mathbf{A}t)$ for calculating the partial derivatives of $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$. It can be anticipated that the lower the computational error between $f(\mathbf{A}t)$ and $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$, the higher the computational accuracy of partial derivatives computed by the MEDM. In our previous work, we derived approximation functions for the partial derivatives of $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$ based on the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM). And two forms of CRAM (PFD and IPF) [1], [9] showed excellent accuracy in computing the partial derivatives of the matrix exponential. Previous studies have shown that the computational accuracy between 32nd order MMPA and 16th order CRAM agree well[10], while the computational efficiency of the MMPA is higher than CRAM. Hence, this subsection presents the application of the MMPA method within the MEDM framework, hereafter referred to as MEDM-MMPA.

Consider an $n \times n$ matrix \mathbf{A} , the partial derivative of its inverse can be given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^{-1}}{\partial x} = -\mathbf{A}^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x} \mathbf{A}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Taking the partial derivative of Eq. (6), the approximation function for the partial derivative of the $e^{\mathbf{A}t}$ based on the MMPA can be derived using Eq. (8)

$$\frac{\partial e^{\mathbf{A}t}}{\partial x} \approx \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^i \mathbf{B}^{j-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial x} \mathbf{B}^{i-j} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Where the matrix \mathbf{B} and $\partial \mathbf{B} / \partial x$ are as follows

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I} + 2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial x} = -2 \frac{t}{c} \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Where $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$ is the partial derivative of the depletion matrix with respect to the one-group cross-section and decay constant of nuclides.

Thus, the vector of sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to the nuclear data is given by

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{D} \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}(t)}{\partial x} \approx \mathbf{D} \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^i \mathbf{B}^{j-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial x} \mathbf{B}^{i-j} \right\} \mathbf{N}_0 \quad (12)$$

Where $\mathbf{N}(t) = [n_1, n_2, \dots, n_n]^T$, and the diagonal matrix \mathbf{D} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} x/n_1 & & & & & \\ & x/n_2 & & & & \\ & & \ddots & & & \\ & & & x/n_n & & \\ & & & & & \dots & \\ & & & & & & x/n_n \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} \quad (13)$$

2.3. The Implementation of MEDM-MMPA Algorithm

This subsection provides the implementation details of MEDM-MMPA algorithm.

The partial derivative of the depletion matrix $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$ possesses a unique mathematical property, in which only one column contains nonzero elements while all others are zero. The expressions for $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$, in which x represents the decay constants and one-group cross sections, are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \lambda_i} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & b_{i \rightarrow 1} & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & -1 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & b_{i \rightarrow j} & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & b_{i \rightarrow n} & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \sigma_{i \rightarrow j}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & -\phi & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \phi & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} \quad (14)$$

Where λ_i is the decay constant of nuclide i , $b_{i \rightarrow j}$ is the decay branching ratio of nuclide i to j , $\sigma_{i \rightarrow j}$ is the one-group cross section of the neutron reaction where nuclide i generates j , and ϕ is the neutron flux.

Since $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$ has only one column with nonzero elements, the product of $(\mathbf{A}t/c - \mathbf{I})^{-1}$ and $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$ in Eq. (11) can be efficiently computed by solving a linear system, which can be written as

$$\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{0}, \dots, \mathbf{y}, \dots, \mathbf{0}] = \left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x} \quad (15)$$

$$\left(\frac{\mathbf{A}t}{c} - \mathbf{I} \right) \mathbf{y} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x} \mathbf{e}_j \quad (16)$$

Where $\mathbf{e}_j = [0, \dots, 1, \dots, 0]^T$ is the j -th column of the identity matrix, corresponding to the column containing the nonzero elements of $\partial \mathbf{A} / \partial x$. Thus, when multiple input parameters are considered, the linear systems associated with these parameters can be solved simultaneously, since they have the same coefficient matrix. The detailed implementation of the MEDM-MMPA is listed in Table I.

Table I. The Implementation of MEDM-MMPA algorithm.

Algorithm: MEDM-MMPA	
1.	Initialization:
2.	Generate matrix: $\mathbf{P} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x_1} \mathbf{e}_{j_1}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x_2} \mathbf{e}_{j_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial x_m} \mathbf{e}_{j_m} \right] \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times m}$
3.	Initialize sensitivity coefficient matrix: $\mathbf{SC} = \mathbf{D} \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{N}(t)}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}(t)}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}(t)}{\partial x_m} \right] = [\mathbf{0}, \dots, \mathbf{0}] \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times m}$
4.	LU factorization: $\mathbf{L} \times \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{A}t/c - \mathbf{I}$
5.	Calculation:
6.	for $i = 1: k$
7.	for $j = 1: i$
8.	$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{N}(0)$
9.	for $z = 1: (i - j)$
10.	$\mathbf{X}_{temp} = \mathbf{X}$
11.	$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}^{-1} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{X}$
12.	$\mathbf{X} = 2\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{X}_{temp}$
13.	end
14.	$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}^{-1} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{X}$
15.	$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U}^{-1} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{P}$ ($\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times m}$)
16.	$\mathbf{Y}^T = \mathbf{M} \mathbf{Y}^T$ ($\mathbf{M} \in \mathbf{R}^{m \times m}$ is the diagonal matrix, $\mathbf{M}[m, m] = \mathbf{X}[j_m]$)
17.	$\mathbf{Y} = -2(t/c) \mathbf{Y}$
18.	for $z = 1: (j - 1)$
19.	$\mathbf{Y}_{temp} = \mathbf{Y}$
20.	$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U}^{-1} \mathbf{L}^{-1} \mathbf{Y}$
21.	$\mathbf{Y} = 2\mathbf{Y} + \mathbf{Y}_{temp}$
22.	end
23.	$\mathbf{Y} = a_i \mathbf{Y}$
24.	$\mathbf{SC} = \mathbf{SC} + \mathbf{Y}$
25.	end
26.	end
27.	$\mathbf{SC} = \mathbf{D} \times \mathbf{SC}$

3. NUMERICAL VALIDATION

This section provides two numerical cases to validate the MEDM-MMPA algorithm:

- Case I is the decay problem, which aims to validate the sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to the decay constants of ^{53m}Fe .
- Case II is based on the depletion benchmark proposed by Argonne National Laboratory (ANL). The direct differentiation method is applied to validate the sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to the one-group microscopic fission cross section of ^{235}U .

3.1. Case I: The Decay of ^{53m}Fe

In this case, the decay chain is shown in Fig.1, and the detailed parameters are listed in Table II. Although this case involves only four nuclides, their decay constants differ by several orders of magnitude. Thus, the depletion matrix of this case is highly stiff, providing a challenging test to evaluate the performance of the MEDM-MMPA method.

Table II. Input parameters for Case I.

Nuclide	Decay Constant (s ⁻¹)	Initial Density (atoms/cm ³)	Depletion Time (s)
^{53m}Fe	$4.548209846 \times 10^{-3}$	1.0×10^{24}	5000
^{53}Fe	$1.357515042 \times 10^{-3}$	0	
^{53}Mn	$5.936359811 \times 10^{-15}$	0	
^{53}Cr	0	0	

Figure 1. The decay chain of the ^{53m}Fe

The analytical solution of the nuclide densities can be obtained by the TTA method. Therefore, the partial derivative of the four nuclides' densities with respect to the decay constant of ^{53}Fe at depletion time of 5000 seconds also have analytical solutions. The comparison between MEDM-MMPA and the analytical solution of sensitivity coefficients are listed in Table III.

Table III. Comparison of results between the MEDM-MMPA and the Analytical Solution

Nuclide	Analytical Solution	MEDM-MMPA	Relative Error
^{53m}Fe	-2.27410×10^1	-2.27455×10^1	1.94×10^{-4}
^{53}Fe	-4.25458×10^{-1}	-4.25458×10^{-1}	-7.10×10^{-10}
^{53}Mn	6.85024×10^{-4}	6.85024×10^{-4}	-1.91×10^{-10}
^{53}Cr	5.42350×10^{-2}	5.42350×10^{-2}	-7.36×10^{-12}

3.2. Case II: The ANL Point Depletion Benchmark

This case is a two-group depletion benchmark problem proposed by ANL[11]. The nuclide transmutation chain of the benchmark is shown in Fig.2. Input parameters including decay constants, two-group cross sections, fission product yields and other related data are available in the reference.

In this case, the one-group microscopic fission cross section of ^{235}U is calculated by collapsing the two-group cross sections. And this paper applies a 0.01% perturbation to this one-group cross section, and the sensitivity coefficients are calculated by the direct differentiation. The comparison of results between MEDM-MMPA and direct differentiation method are listed in Table IV.

Figure 2. The depletion chain of the ANL benchmark

Table IV. Comparison of results between the MEDM-MMPA and the Direct Differentiation Method (sensitivity coefficients $> 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$)

Nuclide	Direct Differentiation	MEDM-MMPA	Relative Error
^{135}I	5.14210×10^{-1}	5.14167×10^{-1}	-8.38×10^{-5}
^{135}Xe	5.14380×10^{-1}	5.14339×10^{-1}	-7.99×10^{-5}
^{147}Nd	6.20059×10^{-1}	6.20002×10^{-1}	-9.30×10^{-5}
^{147}Pm	7.21629×10^{-1}	7.21561×10^{-1}	-9.40×10^{-5}
^{148}Pm	7.32710×10^{-1}	7.32642×10^{-1}	-9.20×10^{-5}
$^{148\text{m}}\text{Pm}$	7.32125×10^{-1}	7.32056×10^{-1}	-9.39×10^{-5}
^{149}Pm	5.67626×10^{-1}	5.67576×10^{-1}	-8.93×10^{-5}
^{149}Sm	5.74692×10^{-1}	5.74639×10^{-1}	-9.23×10^{-5}
^{235}U	-1.93348×10^{-1}	-1.93331×10^{-1}	-9.00×10^{-5}
^{236}U	-9.35988×10^{-2}	-9.35881×10^{-2}	-1.14×10^{-4}
^{237}U	-8.00457×10^{-2}	-8.00343×10^{-2}	-1.42×10^{-4}
^{237}Np	-5.51686×10^{-2}	-5.51617×10^{-2}	-1.25×10^{-4}
^{238}Np	-5.22223×10^{-2}	-5.22193×10^{-2}	-5.65×10^{-5}
^{238}Pu	-4.02262×10^{-2}	-4.02203×10^{-2}	-1.46×10^{-4}

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a method for calculating sensitivity coefficients, termed MEDM-MMPA, which can accurately calculate the sensitivity coefficients of nuclide densities with respect to the nuclear data, including decay constants, microscopic cross section, etc. And the paper also presents the implementation details of the MEDM-MMPA method. The proposed method is validated by two cases: the ^{53m}Fe decay problem and the ANL depletion benchmark. Numerical results show that MEDM-MMPA exhibits very low computational errors. Compared with the conventional method, it can efficiently compute sensitivity coefficients for multiple input parameters. These results indicate that MEDM-MMPA has significant potential for uncertainty and sensitivity analysis in depletion calculations.

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